

Inventory and Cash Management: An Assessment of Cooperative Members' Investment Performance in Ibadan, Oyo State.

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Abstract

The study examines some components of working capital management and performance of agricultural cooperative societies in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study was motivated by the need to determine the influence of these working capital management on cooperative performance in the study area. The specific objectives are to: ascertain the extent to which cash management influences cooperative members return on Investment (ROI) in Oyo State; determine the extent to which inventory management practices influence cooperative members return on Investment (ROI) in Oyo State. The area of study is Oyo State where samples of 139 cooperatives were selected from the population of 213 registered cooperatives in the study area. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. The study employed regression technique, one sample T-test, mean, frequency and percentage in analyzing the data obtained. The study found out that the P-value of 0.031 is less than the alpha value 0.05 and is found to be significant. There is a strong relationship between inventory management on cooperative performance (ROI) at value of (0.987). The study therefore recommends that proper management of various components of working capital need to be maintained to ensure adequate amount of working capital and liquidity.

Keywords: Working Capital, Cash Management, Inventory Management, Return on Investment, Performance, Cooperative Societies.

Introduction

Background of the Study

Working Capital Management may be defined as the regulation, adjustment and control of current assets and current liabilities accounts in such a way that maturing obligations are met and fixed assets are properly serviced. It is a business strategy designed to ensure that a company operates efficiently by monitoring and using its current assets and liabilities to the best effect (Tuovila, 2021). Working Capital Management may be the regulation, adjustment and control of current assets and current liabilities accounts in such a way that maturing obligations are met and fixed assets are properly serviced. It is a business strategy designed to ensure that a company operates efficiently by monitoring and using its current assets and liabilities to the best effect (Tuovila, 2021). The significant effect of working capital management and cooperative performance are presented, thus the purpose of presenting an overview of

working capital management is to provide a backdrop for the study. Working capital management is an area of corporate finance which directly affects the liquidity and performance of the firm (Raheman & Nasr, 2007).

One of the most important working capital components to be managed by all organizations is cash and cash equivalents. It is needed for performing all the activities of a firm, i.e., from acquisition of raw materials to marketing of finished goods.

According to Fasessin, Ayo-Oyebiyi and Folajin (2017), working capital management is the ability to control effectively and efficiently the current assets and current liabilities in a manner that provides the firm with maximum return on its assets and minimizes payments for its liabilities.

Inventory is purchased goods to either build products or keep stock to sell to other companies (Baker & Martin, 2011). Cooperatives use inventory to produce products to turn into account receivables or hold for safety stock to limit demand shock from potential customers. However, inventory constitutes a major part of total working capital. Efficient management of inventory results in maximization of earnings of the shareholders. Inventory is costly to store, therefore, there is always pressure to reduce inventory as part of firms overall cost containment strategies (Brigham & Daves, 2010; Pandey 2010; Okafor and Okonkwo, 2022; Okonkwo, et. al. 2021).

In recent time investors-both in cooperative and none cooperatives businesses are critical and also skeptical about their Return on Assets (ROA), Net Operating Profit (NOP) and Return on Equity (ROE). The vision of the cooperative development policy is to promote members' entrepreneurial capacities so that they can generate adequate surpluses for themselves and create opportunities for economic progress for the public (Oladejo, 2013). For an economy to experience development, two conditions are necessary and sufficient. These are the presence or availability of entrepreneur and providers of external finance (Oladejo, 2013; Okonkwo and Ugwa, 2020; Okonkwo, et. al. 2018). In line with the above assertion as it concerns cooperative businesses, if the available finance is not properly managed the business will collapse and investors will lose their money.

Statement of the Problem

This study was necessitated by the perceived unimpressive performance of cooperative societies that has made the organizational form not to be seen as proactive in solving the business concerns of the populace. Arguably, most of the cooperatives apart from credit cooperatives hardly survive one decade of their business operation. This poor and unsatisfactory performance has been attributed by scholars to poor financial performance (Oladejo, 2013). Return on asset has been negative and assets continue to liquidate without replacement.

According to (Nnadozie et al, 2015) who studied cooperatives in Nigeria, cash management has caused disagreement as people charged with cash management embezzle the money or get involved in frivolous spending. The problem was exacerbated by poor record keeping especially as it relates to account payable and account receivable. All these situations revealed that bankruptcy of some cooperatives can be linked to poor components of working capital management like inventory and cash management. However, the attention of researchers and scholars seem not to have been drawn to ascertain the extent of working capital management in cooperatives and how it affects their performance. In as much as this area has been studied in the context of profit-oriented businesses, findings did not consider peculiarities of cooperatives.

Research Questions

The following research questions are meant to guide the study.

- i. To what extent has cash management influenced cooperatives members return on investment (ROI) in Imo State?
- ii. To what extent have cooperative members' inventory management practices influence return on investment (ROI) in Imo State?

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to determine the influence of working capital management and performance of cooperative societies in Imo State Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study are to:

- i. ascertains the extent cash management influences cooperative members return on Investment (ROI) in Imo State.
- ii. assess the extent to which cooperative members inventory management practices influence return on Investment (ROI) in Imo State.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are designed to guide the study:

- H01:** Cash management does not have significant influence on cooperative members return on Investment (ROI) in Imo State.
- H02:** Cooperative Members Inventory management practices do not have significant influence on return on Investment (ROI) in Imo State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Working Capital Management

According to Aravindan and Ramanathan (2013) working capital management deals with decisions regarding the trade off between liquidity and profitability. Working Capital Management (WCM) refers to all the strategies adopted by the company to manage the relationship between its short-term assets and short term liabilities with the objective to ensure that it continues with its operations and meet its debt obligations when they fall due. In other words, it refers to all aspects of administration of current assets and current liabilities. Efficient working capital management is necessary for achieving both liquidity and profitability of a company. A poor and inefficient working capital management leads to tying up funds in idle assets and reduces the liquidity and profitability of a company (Reddy & Kameswari, 2004). Efficient management of working capital is a fundamental part of the overall corporate strategy. The working capital policies of different companies have an impact on the profitability, liquidity and structural health of the organization. Working capital management represents the decision about the manipulation of ratios which involves managing the relationship between a firm's current assets and current liabilities. One of the main purposes of working capital management is to provide sufficient liquidity to sustain firm's operations and to have to meet its obligations (Ejelly, 2004; Okonkwo, et. al. 2017; Otaokpukpu, et. al. 2017). All firms, regardless of their size and industry need to acquire positive cash flow and liquidity. The way that working capital is managed has also noted unworthy effects on the firm's profitability. For a firm's trading activities, working capital can be considered as a spontaneous fund, and the amount of funds tied up to current assets can exceed that of fixed assets in many firms. In this context, funds committed to working capital can be seen as hidden sources that can be used for improving firm's profitability. Hence it is the fact that working capital management involves a trade - off between profitability and risk.

Components of Working Capital Management

There is often interrelationship among the working capital components which create real challenges for the financial managers. Thus, the different components of working capital management of any organization are: (Edupristine, 2015).

a. Cash Management:

One of the most important working capital components to be managed by all organizations is cash and cash equivalents. It is needed for performing all the activities of a firm, i.e. from acquisition of raw materials to marketing of finished goods. Therefore, it is essential for a firm to maintain an adequate cash balance. One of the important functions of a finance manager is to match the inflows and outflows of cash so as to maintain adequate cash (Edupristine, 2015).

b. Receivables Management

The term receivable is defined as any claim for money owed to the firm from customers arising from sale of goods or services in normal course of business. The term account receivable represents sundry debtors of a firm. It is one of the significant components of working capital next to cash and inventories. The total volume of accounts receivable depends on its credit sale and debt collection policy, these two significantly influence the requirement of working capital. A firm grants trade credit to protect its sales from competitors and to attract potential customers to buy its product at favorable terms (Pandey, 2010; Waweru, 2011). Liberal credit policy increases the volume of sales but at the same time it also increases the investment in receivables. Therefore, examination of costs and benefits associated with credit policy is one of the important tasks of a finance manager.

c. Cost of Maintaining Accounts Receivables:

The following are costs associated with maintaining accounts receivables:

Capital Cost:

There is a time gap between the sale of goods and payment by debtors during which time the firm has to arrange funds for meeting their obligations like payment for raw materials, wages, etc. This additional financing involves some cost, known as capital cost. Collection Cost: Collection costs are the administrative costs incurred by the firm for collecting money from the debtors.

Default Cost:

Default cost is the cost that arises from bad debt losses.

Delinquency Cost:

These costs arise for extending credit to defaulting customers. Such costs are legal charges, costs involved in putting extra effort for collection, costs associated with sending reminders, etc.

Formulation of Credit Policies:

Credit policy has significant impact on the profitability of a concern but it should be ensured that the profit on additional sales arising out of liberal credit policy is sufficiently higher than the cost involved for maintaining additional receivables.

d. Inventory Management:

Inventory is purchased goods to either build products or keep stock to sell to other companies (Baker & Martin, 2011). Cooperatives use inventory to produce products to turn into account receivables or hold for safety stock to limit demand shock from potential customers. However, inventory constitutes a major part of total working capital. Efficient management of inventory results in maximization of earnings of the shareholders. Efficient inventory management consists of managing two conflicting objectives: Minimization of investment in inventory on the one hand; and maintenance of the smooth flow of raw materials for production and sales on the other.

Inventory is costly to store, therefore, there is always pressure to reduce inventory as part of firms overall cost containment strategies (Brigham & Daves, 2010; Pandey 2010).

Therefore, the objective of a finance manager is to calculate the level of inventory where these conflicting interests are reconciled. Like cash, a firm holds inventory for transaction, precautionary and speculative motives.

Inventory Costs:

Besides purchase costs, inventory costs are of two types: Ordering costs and carrying costs.

Ordering Cost:

These costs include variable costs associated with acquisition of materials, like transportation costs, inspection costs, etc. This cost is also known as set-up cost.

Carrying Costs:

These costs include costs associated with holding the inventory such as storage charges, interest on capital, etc.

Cooperative Performance

Performance is the accomplishment of a given task measured against preset known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed.

Performance is defined as an improved product quality, productivity or technical efficiency, service capabilities of a firm, which lead to sustainable profits (Rimantas & Julius, 2011) in their study, defined cooperative performance in terms of key indicators such as returns on investment, satisfaction of members on goods and services provided by cooperatives and education and training of members and employees. The financial ratios, mostly based upon efficiency measures (profit / financial resources), do not seem adequate to estimate cooperative performances. Due to a specific double commitment of cooperative members, cooperatives face a problem of dual performance objectives and find it difficult to establish balanced governance in order to solve this internal conflict of interests called “cooperative dilemma” (Antoine, Pierre & Mario, 2011; Ugwa, et. al. 2015).

Inventory Management and Cooperative Performance

Inventory management is practiced in various organization. Effective inventory management enables organization to reduce total cost by decreasing ordering and holding cost as well as achieving wide scale operational efficiencies. Inventory management system helps to develop quality-based reviews for process improvement that reduces process variability and aim for zero defect. (Ma & Tang, 2001). Having effective inventory management has been of great benefit to agricultural cooperative as they serve their members/patron by selling products, providing quality, timely services and desired products with competitive prices. The cooperative thereby reduces their inventory cost through maintaining effective inventory management system

Theoretical Framework: Risk-Return Trade Off Theory

The risk and return theory by Harry (1952) are one of the most important theories in the field of portfolio management. The risk and return relationship have received considerable attention from researchers in business, economics and finance (Mukherji, Desai & Wright, 2008). Furthermore, every decision with respect to investment is based on risk and return relationship (Richard, Stewart & Franklin, 2008). Relating to that, two conflicting attitudes are always associated with the risk. That is, the risk-seeking behavior and the risk aversion. Risk seekers always prefer choices involving a higher potential loss or a greater probability of a loss and of course with a strong notion of over estimating gains. The main focus of risk-seekers is on the opportunities for gain. Conversely, risk-averters are completely opposite of risk seekers, in the sense that they (risk averters) over estimate losses and underestimate gains. However, in order to integrate the risk and return theory in working capital management, it is imperative to stress

that one of the cardinal decisions in working capital management is the trade-off between liquidity and profitability. If a firm chooses to be liquid it should be at the expense of the profit and vice-versa.

Any of these two conflicting decisions may result in either of excess or shortage of the components of working capital and the current assets of a business. In the same vein, the risk and return theory which is an integral part of the portfolio theory can be associated to working capital when we look inwardly at the ability of a firm or financial manager to determine the collection of assets, or portfolio to be acquired, since it is impossible to own everything, decisions on what the composition of receivables, inventories, incentives and stocks viz-a-viz the profitability concern are all within the context of risk and return theory.

Zariyawati, Annuar, Taufiq and Abdulrahim, (2009) theory of risk and return states that investment with a higher risk may create a higher return, thus a firm with a high liquidity in working capital will have a low risk of failing to meet its obligations, and low profitability at the same time. That is, the greater the amount of NWC, the less risk-prone the firm is and the greater the NWC, the more liquid is the firm therefore, the less likely it is to become technically insolvent. Conversely, lower of NWC and liquidity are associated with increasing levels of risk. The relationship between liquidity, NWC and risk is such that if either NWC or liquidity increases, the firm's risk decreases (Zariyawati et al, 2009).

Empirical Review

Waithaka (2012) studied the relationship between working capital management practices and financial performance of agricultural companies listed at the Nairobi securities exchange in Kenya. The study adopted a Correlational or Prospective Research Design which attempted to explore the relationship between working capital management and financial performance to make predictions with the use of two or more variables for each. The findings of the study were that, financial performance was positively related to Efficiency of Cash Management (ECM), Efficiency of Receivables Management (ERM) and Efficiency of Inventory Management (EIM).

Padachi (2006) had undertaken a study with the objective of examining the effect of accounts receivables days, inventories days, account payable days and cash conversion cycle on return on total assets. He also analyses the tendency in working capital requirements of firms for a sample of 58 small manufacturing firms in Mauritius for the period 1998-2003. Using pooled OLS and fixed effect regression model, he established that lower profitability was related with higher investment in receivables and inventories. The findings also reveal a rising tendency in the short-term component of financing working capital.

Adediran, Josiah, Bosun-Fakunle and Imuzeze,(2012) investigated the impact of working capital management on the profitability of a sample of 30 SME's in Nigeria, covering the single period of 2009. Data was collected from secondary sources (financial statement) and was analyzed using the multiple regression analysis. The results which are robust to the presence of endogeneity, demonstrate that managers can create value by reducing their firm's number of day's accounts receivable and inventories. Equally, shortening the cash conversion cycle also improves the firm's profitability.

Akino, Olayinka and Olufisayo (2012) carried out a detailed study on the determinants of working capital requirements of thirty non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2004 and 2011. Panel data methodology was employed and Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) used as estimation technique. The Working capital requirement (firm's networking capital deflated by total assets) was used as dependent variable. Regression results reveal that five explanatory variables- firm's leverage, size, industry classification, return on asset and operating cycle are significant factors that determine the firms' working capital requirements for the period under study. The outcome of this study supports the findings of some previous studies and is also consistent with financial theory.

Gap in Literature

From the review of literature, it was observed that previous researchers like (Akoto, Awunyo and Angmor, 2013; Ponsian, Kiemi, Gwatako and Halim, 2014; Nyarige and Olweny, 2014) focused only on account receivables and cash positions as only components of working capital but this study used two components of working capital: inventory management and cash management. Another gap which this study tries to fill is that the focus is on Credit and Thrift cooperatives Societies.

Other studies examined cooperatives from an holistic perspective while this study adopted a type of cooperative in assessing the influence of two components of working capital management on cooperative performance.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study is the survey research design.

Sources of Data

Two major sources of data were referred to in the course of this study, the conventional sources of primary and secondary data. Data for this study was collected mainly from primary source. Data were gathered from the primary source through questionnaire that was self-administered while secondary source of information were journals, textbooks and other records that are relevant to the study.

Area of the Study

This study was carried out in South-Western part of Nigeria specifically at Ibadan metropolis in Oyo State. The researcher picked this zone because it has more numbers of functional credit and thrift cooperatives in the State.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of all registered and active credit and thrift cooperative societies in Ibadan, Oyo State. From the data gotten from the State Ministry of Cooperative (2018) report, there are a total of 1184 registered credit and thrift cooperative societies that are active and functional with membership strength of 38,520.

Sample Size Determination and Sampling Technique

Multistage sampling technique was used in this study. All credit and thrift cooperative societies in the area were categorized into the three zones in the state. In stage one, the local government areas that are predominantly CTCS was purposively selected from each of the three zones: Ibadan North-East, Ibadan North-West and Ibadan Central. In stage two, all the registered cooperatives in these selected local governments were selected. In stage three, all the cooperatives who have audited accounts for 2019 and 2020 were selected.

To determine the sample size for the study, Taro Yamani formula was used

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n = Sample size

N = Desired sample size

1 = Constant

e = The degree of error expected

N = 213

e = 0.05

Therefore,

$$n = \frac{213}{1 + 213(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{213}{1 + 213 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{213}{1.5325}$$

$$n = 139$$

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection is the structured questionnaire designed by the researcher in line with the objectives of the study. As a result, the questionnaire was designed to be filled by executive member of these cooperative in order to generate the missing data.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

Reliability test to check the consistency of the measuring instrument over time was conducted in a test-retest manner, using Pearson Correlation coefficient. Under this procedure the instrument administered to a sample of 12 executive members of the selected cooperatives in the area of study. Their responses were noted and appropriately coded. Thereafter the same instrument was administered to the same group of farmers after 3 weeks and their first and second responses were examined using Pearson Correlation Analysis. The result showed a test result of 0.790 affirming that the instrument is reliable.

Method and tools for Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, means and percentages was used to analyze the data obtained to address the objectives of the study. Also inferential statistics, such as one sample t-test and regression was employed to address the research questions and to test the promulgated hypotheses. Specifically, mean rating and descriptive statistics were used to address the research questions while f-test, t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 5% level of significance.

Objective number one was achieved using one sample t-test.

Objective number two was achieved using regression analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 was the software employed in the analysis of the data generated

Model Specification

The relationship between the dependent and independent variable were measured by a linear regression expressed as: $y = a + bx$ 1

Considering the objectives and hypotheses in chapter one, a model was specified to examine the relationship between inventory and cash management and performance of cooperative societies in Imo state, Nigeria.

The multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the net cash flow, effect of stock level, turnover ratio and invoice lead time on performance of cooperatives measured by return on investment (ROI).

The relationship between the dependent variable (Return on investment which is a measure of performance) and independent variables (net cashflow, stock level, turnover ratio and invoice lead time) which are components of working capital is stated thus:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots 2$$

Where y = Cooperative performance (proxied by return on investment)

a = constant term

x_1 = cash and bank proxied by net cash flow

x_2 = inventory level proxied by stock level

Therefore,

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where: Y= return on investment

a= constant term

β_1 - β_4 = parameter of estimate

x_1 = net cash flow

x_2 =stock level

x_3 =turnover ratio

x_4 = Invoice lead time

e= error term

Linear:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + e \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 2}$$

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Effect of changes in cash items on cooperative performance

Effects of Cash Position	SD	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Remark
Ability to meet immediate obligation	33	48	17	12	10	3.68	Accept
Payment to suppliers	28	51	11	23	7	3.58	Accept
Enhancing operating activities	36	49	8	15	12	3.68	Accept
Acquiring new production facilities	16	29	20	36	19	2.89	Reject
Investing activities	21	37	23	34	5	3.29	Accept
Redeeming investment in other firms	29	40	16	32	3	3.50	Accept
Financing activities	36	44	8	23	9	3.63	Accept
Obtaining or returning financial resources from members to others	38	50	10	16	6	3.82	Accept
Redemption of loans	11	23	7	49	40	2.55	Reject
Redemption of members equities	17	28	2	36	37	2.6	Reject
Payment of patronage refunds	34	39	13	20	14	3.50	Accept

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 4.6 analyzed effect of changes in cash items on cooperative performance. Findings revealed that changes in cash items had significant effects on ability of the cooperative to meet immediate financial obligations, payment to suppliers, enhance operating activities, obtaining financial resources and payment of patronage refund. However, changes in cash items did not have significant effect on acquisition of new production facilities and redemption of members loans and equities. Since over 75% of factors which were indicators of cooperative performance were significantly affected by changes in cash item, the researcher concluded that changes in cash item had significant effect on performance of cooperatives.

Table 4.7: Effects of changes in inventory level on cooperative performance

Effect	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Remark
Affect revenue stream of cooperative	39	57	10	20	4	4.14	Accept
Increase/decrease in cash flow	32	46	8	29	5	3.59	Accept
Affect quantum of fund available for investment	11	37	6	54	12	2.84	Reject
Affect the rate of interest on fund	18	30	16	52	4	3.05	Accept
Affect inventory control cost	31	59	15	13	2	3.87	Accept

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 4.7 analyzed the effects of changes in inventory levels on cooperative performance. Out of the five variables used, effects of change in inventory levels were significant on four. These include revenue stream, cashflow, interest rate on funds and inventory control cost. The only variable that was not significant was quantum of fund available for investment. Since four out of five factors were significant, the researcher concluded that changes in inventory control had significant effect on cooperative performance.

Regression Estimates showing the effect of Cash Management, inventory, Account Receivables and Accounts Payable on cooperative performance (ROI)

Model	B	Std Error	Beta	T	Sig
Constant	-.593	.140		-4.224	.000
Cash mgt	.421	.143	.414	2.932	.004
inventory	.120	.066	.102	1.819	.071
Acct Receivable	.176	.157	.162	1.124	.263
Acct Payable	.348	.126	.298	2.756	.007
R	.956 ^a				
R ²	.913				
Adj. R ²	.910				
F-statistics	301.699				

a. Predictors: (Constant), Account Payable, Inventory, Cash Management, Account Receivable

The data is analyzed based on the SPSS output

R-squared (R^2) = 0.913

Adjusted R-squared (R^2) = 0.910

F-statistics = 301.699

The regression model is summarized thus,

$Y = F(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4)$

We therefore estimate that

$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + U_t$

Filing the regression line we have

Cooperative Performance = $-.593 + 0.421_{CM} + 0.120_{INVT} + 0.176_{AR} + 0.348_{AP} + U_t$

The implication of the above estimation is that about 91.3% of the variation in the dependent variable (Cooperative performance) was explained by the independent variables (cash management, Inventory, Account Receivable and Account Payable) This can be interpreted as a very strong positive relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The adjusted R^2 means that our model has accounted

for 91% of the variance in the dependent variable, the remaining 9% of the variation in cooperative performance is explained by stochastic factors. The F-statistics with value of 301.699 explains that the independent variables jointly explained the variation that occurred in the dependent variables and thus reveals the model to have a good fit for prediction.

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Cash management does not have significant influence on cooperative members return on investment (ROI) in Imo State.

Decision:

Since the calculated t-value is higher than the table t-value and p-value is significant, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, we conclude that management of cash and bank items influence cooperative performance.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Inventory management does not have significant effect cooperative performance

Decision:

The table revealed that inventory level was significant at 0.05 level of significant with sig value $0.07 < 0.05$, the null hypothesis was rejected. So, we conclude that inventory management has significant effect on cooperative performance.

Discussion of Findings

The findings on Hypothesis 1 reveal a p-value of 0.004 which is less than 5% confidence interval. This means that we reject the null hypothesis which states that cash management does not have significant influence on cooperative members return on investment (ROI) in Imo state and accept the alternative which states that cash management has significant influence on cooperative members return on investment (ROI) in Imo state. The analysis further reveals that effect of changes in cash and bank items on cooperative performance helps with the ability to meet immediate obligation, ensure payment to suppliers, enhance operating activities, redeem investment in other firms, financing activities, obtaining or returning financial resources from members to others, and payment of patronage refunds. This is similar to findings made in Raheman and Nasir (2007). However, it was also found that the effect of changes in cash and bank items on cooperative performance does not help acquire new production facilities, investing activities, redemption of loans and redemption of members' equities.

The analysis on hypothesis two reveal that the effects of changes in inventory level on cooperative performance affect revenue stream of cooperative, increases/decreases in cash flow, and affect inventory control cost. However, it was found that the effects of changes in inventory level on cooperative performance does not affect quantum of fund available for investment and does not affect the rate of interest on funds.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

From the findings of the research work, it can be summarized that:

- i. The P-value of 0.004 which is less than 5% confidence interval is significant. This means that cash management has significant influence on cooperative members return on investment (ROI) in Imo state.
- ii. There is a strong relationship between inventory management on cooperative performance (ROI) (0.913). This shows that 91.3% of the changes in the Cooperative return on investment

were explained by the variables in the model. Therefore, the effects of changes in inventory level on cooperative performance affect revenue stream of cooperative, increases/decreases in cash flow, and affect inventory control cost.

However, it was found that the effects of changes in inventory level on cooperative performance does not affect quantum of fund available for investment and does not affect the rate of interest on funds.

Conclusion

The study established that effective working capital performance provides a critical insight into the state of the cooperatives financial position. It is a crucial indicator of financial fitness. It was noted that the cooperatives' ability to properly manage current asset and the association liabilities or current obligations may determine how well it is able to survive in the short run.

Specifically, the findings of the study indicates that cash management has significant influence on cooperative members return on investment (ROI) in Imo state, it revealed that there is a strong relationship between inventory management and cooperative performance.

Recommendations

Based on the analysis and findings of this study, the researcher therefore recommends that:

- i. Proper management of various components of working capital should be maintained to ensure adequate amount of working capital and liquidity in order to successfully run the cooperative. This can be achieved through maintaining proper level of net working capital by trying to control the growth rate of current assets as compared to some extent.
- ii. That control measures need to be taken on stock because it represents cash and a substantial share of fund is invested in the cooperatives inventory. A good inventory system will help in preventing stock outs and help in decision making in the procurement function.

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